

NANOTUBE-BUCKYPAPER/POLYURETHANE COMPOSITES WITH ENHANCED MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Nanotube (NT) papers, or buckypapers, were fabricated by filtering suspensions of either carbon nanotubes (CNTs) or boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) and modified by incorporation of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU). The resulting NT-TPU composite buckypapers (up to 90% nanotubes by weight) retained the low-density, porous structure typical of buckypaper. The tensile properties were significantly improved by this approach and could be adjusted by changing the ratio of nanotubes to TPU. Modification with TPU also improves the flexibility and robustness of the papers, which are easier to handle and offer opportunities for further composites production by infiltration with other polymers or assembly with other fiber fabrics to form hybrid composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and boron nitride nanotubes (BNNTs) have analogous structures and exhibit exceptional mechanical properties combined with low density and high aspect ratio. These related nanomaterials offer different but complementary multifunctional properties including good electrical conductivity for CNTs and, for BNNTs, electrical insulation, higher thermal stability and polarizability, among other differences. Therefore, development of macroscopic materials and composites employing both types of nanotubes is of interest. One such nanotube material form that has received significant attention in the CNT literature is buckypaper. Buckypapers are nanotube sheets, usually non-woven like conventional paper, which can be fabricated by filtration of nanotubes dispersed in liquid. CNT buckypaper is of interest for applications including electromagnetic shielding [1], heat conductors [2], fire retardancy [3], electrodes [4,5] and as reinforcement for polymer composites [6-8]. We recently reported some of the first work with free-standing BNNT buckypapers and their composites [9,10], which have not been comparably well-developed due to a lack of efficient synthetic methods to produce large quantities of BNNTs. Recent reports, including a pilot-scale process for synthesis of small diameter, high quality BNNT (~ 200 g/day demonstrated capacity) from our team [10,11], have demonstrated significant advances in BNNT production and therefore the buckypaper form of nanotube material is accessible with both CNTs and BNNTs.

A key limitation to the application of buckypaper is that the mechanical properties of sheets prepared by filtration of NT suspensions are typically modest and universally much weaker than individual nanotubes. One approach used to improve the mechanical properties of buckypaper sheets is the infiltration of polymers as a binder. We recently reported significant improvements in the tensile properties of BNNT buckypaper through modification with TPU [9], where the properties were also tailorable through controlling the nanotube-to-polyurethane ratio. Polyurethane (TPU) is among the most versatile polymer materials today, consisting of nanophase separated hard segments and soft segments, and can be tailored according to the desired application requirements. The approach can also be applied with CNT buckypapers and in this manuscript we present a comparative study of the

influence of the processing conditions on the tensile properties of BNNT-TPU and MWCNT-TPU composite buckypapers. Two different methods, infiltration of pre-formed buckypapers and a one-step filtration, were employed to produce light weight NT-TPU nanocomposite sheets with high content of NTs (up to 90 wt%) while retaining the porous structure typical of buckypapers. The tensile properties were significantly improved by this approach and could be adjusted by changing the ratio of nanotubes to TPU. Such nanocomposite sheets are easy to handle and can be stretched, folded and also show potential to use as an intermediate step in the production of other composites by further impregnation with polymer or integration with other fiber fabrics.

2 MATERIALS & METHODS

The BNNT material was manufactured using an induction thermal plasma technique [10,11], and was purified using thermal and solvent treatments. Commercially available multi-walled CNTs (MWCNTs; Nanocyl NC7000) were used for production of MWCNT buckypapers. To fabricate nonwoven NT buckypaper, MWCNTs or BNNTs were dispersed in alcohol using sonication and then the dispersion was vacuum-filtered through a 20 μm pore size polycarbonate membrane to produce ~3.5 cm diameter buckypapers using standard laboratory glassware. Larger buckypapers were produced using vacuum table that accommodates rectangular funnels up to 30 \times 30 cm in size. The as-filtered buckypaper was sandwiched between sheets of parchment and compressed. After partial drying at room temperature under compression, the buckypaper was further dried by baking at 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h. Examples of the starting materials (BNNTs and MWCNTs) and their buckypapers are shown in Figure 1. The thermoplastic ester-based polyurethane (TPU) sold as a film adhesive product UAF 472, was supplied by Adhesive Films, Inc.

Figure 1: BNNTs (left images) and MWCNTs (right images) in powder and buckypaper forms

TPU-NT nanocomposite sheets were prepared by two methods: by TPU infiltration of the preformed buckypaper and by a one-step filtration method where a NT-TPU suspension in different solvents is filtered to form the nanocomposite buckypaper. In the infiltration method the pristine buckypaper was immersed in a TPU solution in THF (40 mg/mL) for 24 hours before removing the solution and drying on a Teflon film. In the one-step filtration method TPU and NTs were mixed at a 5:1 weight ratio in THF or THF/Methanol mixtures with bath sonication for 30 min to form a homogeneous suspension. This suspension was filtered through a PTFE filter membrane with an average pore diameter of 0.2 μm . After filtration, the composite was sandwiched between sheets of parchment and dried at room temperature overnight.

The neat and TPU-NT buckypapers were characterized scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Hitachi High Technologies S-4700) and mechanical properties were assessed by testing free-standing rectangular specimens under tension until failure. A micro-tensile test frame (Fullam Substage Test Frame) was used to measure the elastic modulus (E), ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and ultimate tensile strain (ϵ_{max}). Repeated tests (at least three strips of each material) were performed using a displacement rate of 1 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Photographs of the NT-TPU composite buckypapers are shown in Figure 2. As seen from Table 2, the buckypaper density increases by incorporation of TPU but remains low in comparison to TPU (1.17 g/cm³). The porous nanotube-network morphology characteristic of buckypaper is also retained (e.g., Figure 3). For fabrication by infiltration of pre-formed buckypapers, the TPU content is higher for MWCNT than for BNNT buckypapers. This could indicate a better wetting of MWCNTs with TPU than is achieved for BNNTs. Changing the concentration of the TPU solution or the infiltration time was not a significant factor in the final TPU content. However, the one-step filtration method enabled control of the TPU content by varying the volume ratios of good and poor solvents for TPU (i.e., THF and methanol). Increasing the amount of the poor solvent (methanol) resulted in increasing TPU content.

Table 1. Characteristics of neat NT buckypapers and NT-TPU buckypapers

Sample	Method	Solvent (Methanol vol.%)	NT/TPU (wt. ratio)	Density (g/cm ³)
BNNT buckypapers				
BNNT	Filtration	Methanol	100:0	0.38
BN83PU17	Infiltration	THF	83:17	0.50
BN93PU7	One-step filtration	THF	93:7	0.51
BN75PU25	One-step filtration	THF/Methanol (44)	75:25	0.59
BN25PU75	One-step filtration	THF/Methanol (50)	25:75	0.75
MWCNT buckypapers				
MWCNT	Filtration	Methanol	100:0	0.25
CN60PU40	Infiltration	THF	60:40	0.57
CN75PU25	One-step filtration	THF	75:25	0.29
CN30PU70	One-step filtration	THF/Methanol (50)	30:70	0.81

Figure 2. NT-TPU composite buckypapers. The top row shows thicker composite buckypapers (Left: BNNT, Right: MWCNT) prepared by infiltration of pre-formed buckypapers, while the bottom row shows examples of BNNT-TPU buckypapers produced by the one-step filtration approach.

Figure 3. SEM images of NT-TPU composite buckypaper. The images shown here are for composite buckypaper prepared by the infiltration method.

The tensile properties of both BNNT-TPU and MWCNT-TPU composite buckypapers are shown in Figure 4. The pristine buckypapers displayed similar properties (elastic modulus \sim 100-300 MPa, ultimate strength \sim 1-2 MPa, failure strain \sim 0.5-1%). In both cases, infiltration with TPU increases properties but with a larger effect on the strength of the MWCNT paper suggesting better NT-TPU interaction in the case of MWCNTs. This issue can likely be addressed by functionalization of the BNNTs. Composite buckypapers produced by the one-step filtration approach show higher strength and stiffness than either neat buckypaper or TPU on their own, along with a trend of increasing strength and stiffness with increasing TPU content. Note that Figure 4 shows the yield strength for TPU, which did not fail within the displacement limit of the test. For the NT-TPU, the samples yield only slightly and the reported yield strengths are close to the maximum strengths. The BNNT-TPU buckypaper properties became qualitatively different at high TPU-content. At the highest TPU content evaluated, the trend of increasing modulus is reversed and the BNNT-TPU buckypapers are lower stiffness (although still higher than TPU), higher density, and have much higher strain at failure (\sim 2000 times higher than the BNNT buckypaper) approaching that of neat TPU. This was not observed for CNT buckypapers although the maximum TPU content evaluated there was slightly lower than in the BNNT case. The significantly improved mechanical properties should be advantageous for employing buckypapers in multifunctional applications and also suggests use of TPU-NT buckypapers as in intermediate step in the fabrication of other composites.

Figure 4. Tensile properties of (a,b) BNNT-TPU composite buckypapers and (c,d) MWCNT-TPU composite buckypapers. The * symbol indicates NT-TPU prepared by infiltration of pre-formed buckypapers. All other composite buckypapers were prepared by the one-step filtration approach.

4 EXAMPLE CASE: UHMWPE/BP HYBRID LAMINATES

With the improved mechanical properties, the NT-TPU composite buckypapers are stronger, more flexible/ foldable and generally more robust, which gives an added benefit in terms of ease of handling and integration into other composite materials. As an example case for integration of NT-TPU buckypapers into a hybrid composite, UHMWPE fabric laminates containing five buckypaper layers are shown in Figure 5. These laminates were produced using MWCNT buckypaper modified by infiltration of TPU as this combination of material and method was the most readily scalable. Peel tests have shown that the UHMWPE fabric layers are effectively laminated when MWCNT-TPU buckypapers are inserted as interlaminar layers [12], in contrast to neat MWCNT buckypapers where the dry buckypaper presents little strength in peel. Our previously reported Charpy results for MWCNT-TPU/UHMWPE laminates [12] indicated that the absorbed energies were very similar to a baseline laminate (no buckypaper), possibly with a small decrease (~5%) with buckypapers near the front face and a small increase (5-10%) with buckypapers near the middle or back face, and that the failed coupons typically showed a disbanding of the fabric layers in the back half of the laminate (Figure 5). Repeated fabrication and testing with the MWCNT-TPU buckypapers near the back face and varying buckypaper properties supports the 5-10% increase in absorbed energy with MWCNT-TPU buckypaper interlayers integrated near the back face.

Figure 4. UHMWPE fiber fabric laminate with MWCNT-TPU composite buckypapers inserted as interlaminar layers.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, two approaches for modification of nanotube buckypapers were observed to significantly improve the tensile properties of both MWCNT and BNNT buckypapers, while retaining a porous morphology. The TPU polymer selected appears to interact more favorably with CNTs and other selections of polymer may be more favourable for BNNT buckypaper. The properties of the NT-TPU composite buckypapers were adjusted by varying the ratio of nanotubes to polyurethane. The improved properties and retained porosity also suggest NT-TPU buckypapers are interesting as an intermediate to preparation of other high-nanotube-content polymer nanocomposites and hybrid composites. Integration of MWCNT-TPU as an interlaminar layer in a hybrid structure with UHMWPE fiber fabric resulted in similar laminate quality to the baseline laminates and a small increase (~5%) in energy absorption in Charpy tests if the buckypaper layers were located towards the back face of the laminate.

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